

VARIATION OF APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME OF NON-ELECTROLYTES IN SOLUTION WITH CONCENTRATION. PART II.

BY S. O. SHUKLA AND W. V. BHAGWAT

The apparent molar volume of non-electrolytes does not seem to vary very much with concentration. This is true of binary and ternary mixtures. The systems urea, glucose, and water; glucose acetamide and water; ethyl acetate, toluene and benzene, and ethyl acetate, benzene and carbon tetrachloride have been studied.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 186) we have shown that apparent molar volume of a non-electrolyte in solution does not seem to vary very much with variation in concentration. The work is extended in this paper. For binary mixture the expression used is

$$\frac{M}{D} / \frac{m_1}{d_1} = 1 + mx - x$$

where M , D , m_1 , d_1 and x have the same significance as given in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

x	M/D	$\frac{M/D}{m_1/d_1}$	m	x	M/D	$\frac{M/D}{m_1/d_1}$	m
(1) CBr_4 in CCl_4 ($m_1/d_1=97.011$).				(2) Tetranitromethane in benzene ($m_1/d_1=69.84$).			
0.1438	97.83	1.0084	1.058	0.3377	100.9	1.1231	1.364
0.2097	103.9	1.0710	1.038	0.5082	108.6	1.1798	1.354
0.2945	99.17	1.0223	1.075	0.6736	111.1	1.2366	1.351
0.3746	99.88	1.0296	1.079	0.8561	116.2	1.2934	1.343
0.4211	100.2	1.0328	1.077				
(3) Glucose in water ($m_1/d_1=18.05$).				(4) Urea in formamide ($m_1/d_1=38.83$).			
0.006582	18.69	1.0354	6.38	0.02622	39.06	1.0059	1.158
0.007741	18.78	1.0404	6.22	0.03824	39.08	1.0084	1.158
0.01198	19.15	1.0809	6.09	0.04735	39.12	1.0077	1.162
				0.05853	39.17	1.0087	1.149
(5) Fructose in pyridine ($m_1/d_1=81.16$).				(6) Urea in methyl alcohol ($m_1/d_1=40.59$).			
0.02507	82.04	1.0109	1.43	0.06480	40.34	0.9938	0.802
0.03217	82.24	1.0133	1.42	0.06756	40.27	0.9928	0.868
0.06503	83.08	1.0236	1.38	0.08000	40.26	0.9921	0.863
				0.08194	40.19	0.9918	0.897
				0.1028	40.05	0.9901	0.878
						0.9866	0.869
(7) Urea in EtOH ($m_1/d_1=58.76$).				(8) Thiourea in pyridine ($m_1/d_1=81.12$).			
0.01037	58.55	0.9964	0.852	0.04214	78.44	98.17	0.565
0.01547	58.41	0.9940	0.812	0.06132	78.98	97.36	0.869
0.02054	58.33	0.9927	0.644	0.07741	78.39	98.63	0.564
0.03232	58.09	0.9884	0.641	0.08561	78.23	95.43	0.583
0.04007	57.94	0.9860	0.650	0.09493	77.78	95.88	0.566
				0.1019	77.64	85.71	0.578

Results of sections (1) and (2) have been calculated on the basis of parachor values of Hammick and Wilmut (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 32) and from Ray's work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 843; 1935, 12, 404).

Ternary System.

For ternary mixture containing x and y molar fractions of solutes whose molecular weights are m_1 and m_2 , we have shown in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) that

$$M/D = (1-x-y)v_1 + xv_2 + yv_3,$$

where v_1 , v_2 , and v_3 are the molar volumes in solution for the solvent and solutes; and M and D are the mean molecular weight and the density of the solutions.

In calculating the molar volumes of glucose, acetamide and urea, the densities employed are those observed by us in solution and given in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). For liquids, the densities of pure liquids at the corresponding temperatures have been substituted.

TABLE II

Molecular volume.

Substance.	$m/d.$	Substance.	$m/d.$
Benzene	$78/0.8661 = 90.071$	Glucose	$= 100.28$
Toluene	$92/0.8558 = 107.501$	Urea	$60/1.345 = 44.61$
Ethyl acetate	$88/0.8907 = 98.795$	Acetamide	$59/1.065 = 55.39$
Carbon tetrachloride	$154/1.678 = 97.592$		

For glucose the molecular volume v_2 is found from the expression $v_2/v_1 = m$. The value of m is 5.553 and v_1 for water is at the same temperature $18/0.997 = 18.05$. Hence $v_2 = 18.05 \times 5.553 = 100.28$.

TABLE III

Ethyl acetate-toluene-benzene system.

$M/D.$	$(1-x-y)v_1 + xv_2 + yv_3.$
(1) $\frac{86.06}{0.8693} = 99.99$	$0.3393 \times 90.07 + 0.3114 \times 98.769 + 0.3493 \times 107.501 = 98.80$
(2) $\frac{86.22}{0.8735} = 98.72$	$0.2764 \times 90.07 + 0.4868 \times 98.8 + 0.2368 \times 107.5 = 98.44$
(3) $\frac{86.71}{0.8675} = 99.95$	$0.3008 \times 90.07 + 0.2874 \times 98.8 + 0.4118 \times 107.5 = 99.73$
(4) $\frac{86.88}{0.8714} = 99.70$	$0.2023 \times 90.07 + 0.3636 \times 98.8 + 0.3741 \times 107.5 = 98.75$
(5) $\frac{85.55}{0.8672} = 98.66$	$0.3961 \times 90.07 + 0.2346 \times 98.8 + 0.3693 \times 107.5 = 98.54$

Ethyl acetate-benzene-carbon tetrachloride system.

$M/D.$	$(1-x-y)v_1 + xv_2 + yv_3.$
(1) $\frac{106.9}{1.117} = 95.74$	$0.3448 \times 90.07 + 0.3115 \times 97.59 + 0.3437 \times 98.8 = 95.63$
(2) $\frac{110.8}{1.150} = 95.15$	$0.3114 \times 90.07 + 0.3924 \times 97.59 + 0.2962 \times 98.8 = 95.80$
(3) $\frac{100.1}{1.058} = 94.61$	$0.4649 \times 90.07 + 0.2539 \times 97.59 + 0.2812 \times 98.8 = 94.70$

$$(4) \frac{102.4}{1.078} = 94.97 \quad 0.2807 \times 90.07 + 0.2770 \times 97.59 + 0.4417 \times 98.8 = 96.19$$

$$(5) \frac{119.3}{1.235} = 96.61 \quad 0.2846 \times 90.07 + 0.5060 \times 97.59 + 0.2394 \times 98.8 = 96.06$$

Glucose-acetamide-water system.

$$(1-x-y) v_1 + xv_2 + yv_3$$

$$(1) \frac{31.2}{1.087} = 28.7 \quad 0.023 \times 100.28 + 0.2233 \times 55.39 + 0.7537 \times 18.05 = 28.44$$

$$(2) \frac{29.76}{1.092} = 27.26 \quad 0.0268 \times 100.28 + 0.1735 \times 55.39 + 0.7980 \times 18.05 = 26.975$$

$$(3) \frac{28.30}{1.087} = 26.06 \quad 0.02616 \times 100.28 + 0.1719 \times 55.39 + 0.8019 \times 18.05 = 26.612$$

$$(4) \frac{28.24}{1.071} = 26.36 \quad 0.1701 \times 100.28 + 0.0189 \times 55.39 + 0.8110 \times 18.05 = 26.815$$

$$(5) \frac{30.97}{1.069} = 28.97 \quad 0.2395 \times 100.28 + 0.0177 \times 55.39 + 0.7428 \times 18.05 = 28.72$$

Urea-glucose-water system.

M/D.

$$(1-x-y) v_1 + xv_2 + yv_3$$

$$(1) \frac{26.68}{1.140} = 23.05 \quad 0.9628 \times 44.61 + 0.02853 \times 100.28 + 0.8752 \times 18.05 = 22.956$$

$$(2) \frac{27.61}{1.207} = 24.52 \quad 0.1207 \times 44.61 + 0.02805 \times 100.28 + 0.8513 \times 18.05 = 23.566$$

$$(3) \frac{28.63}{1.159} = 24.73 \quad 0.1392 \times 44.61 + 0.0297 \times 100.28 + 0.8311 \times 18.05 = 24.198$$

$$(4) \frac{25.93}{1.133} = 22.89 \quad 0.07600 \times 44.61 + 0.02919 \times 100.28 + 0.8942 \times 18.05 = 22.256$$

$$(5) \frac{26.44}{1.132} = 23.35 \quad 0.1224 \times 44.61 + 0.0203 \times 100.28 + 0.8573 \times 18.05 = 23.571$$

$$(6) \frac{27.39}{1.144} = 23.94 \quad 0.1463 \times 44.61 + 0.0200 \times 100.28 + 0.8337 \times 18.05 = 23.577$$

$$(7) \frac{24.79}{1.116} = 23.22 \quad 0.0778 \times 44.61 + 0.0216 \times 100.28 + 0.9006 \times 18.05 = 21.896$$

$$(8) \frac{25.47}{1.122} = 22.70 \quad 0.0963 \times 44.61 + 0.0211 \times 110.28 + 0.8826 \times 18.05 = 22.345$$